

A spatiotemporal ensemble machine learning framework for generating global land cover time-series maps (2000–2025+)

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Abstract

Existing global land cover products often disagree due to differences in input data, methods, and legend design. We present an ensemble framework that integrates multiple products with environmental covariates using random forest classification to produce annual 30 m land cover maps (2000–2025+). Training samples (~77 million points) undergo quality control combining Bayesian map fusion and confident learning to reduce label noise. A pilot over the conterminous United States achieves 74% and 86% overall accuracy at level 1 and level 2 classifications. Outputs include discrete classifications, class probabilities, and pixel-level uncertainty estimates.

Keywords: Land cover mapping, ensemble modeling, space-time modeling

1. Introduction

Land cover regulates the exchange of energy, water, and carbon between the land and atmosphere. Changes driven by agricultural expansion, urbanization, deforestation, and climate feedbacks (Pielke et al. 2002) disrupt ecosystem services, drive biodiversity loss (Foley et al. 2005), modify hydrological regimes, and accelerate soil degradation. Understanding and quantifying these dynamics are therefore central to environmental science and policy. Land cover maps serve as essential inputs for greenhouse gas inventories (Hong et al. 2021), climate impact assessments (Sy and Quesada 2020), and land use planning (Winkler et al. 2021). As pressures on land resources intensify, the need for accurate, high-resolution, and temporally consistent global land cover information continues to grow.

Over the past two decades, the remote sensing community has developed numerous global land cover products, including ESA Climate Change Initiative (ESA CCI; ESA 2017), the MCD12Q1 MODIS/Terra+Aqua (Friedl and Sulla-Menashe 2022), the Copernicus Global Land Service (CGLS-LC100; Buchhorn et al. 2020), the GLC_FCS30D (Zhang et al. 2024), the ESRI land cover (Karra et al. 2021), and the UMD GLAD annual land cover and land use (GLCLUC; Potapov et al. 2022).

Published in “Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI 2026) – Poster Papers”, edited by Haosheng Huang and Nico Van de Weghe, GeoAI 2026, 3-6 June 2026, Ghent, Belgium.

This contribution underwent single-blind peer review based on the extended abstract.

However, these products often differ due to differences in satellite data sources, reference data sample quality, classification algorithms, and legend design (Herold et al. 2016; Fritz, See, and Rembold 2010). No single product demonstrates uniform accuracy: a dataset performing well in tropical forests may perform poorly in savannas, while one optimized for temperate croplands may misclassify dryland agriculture. Consequently, users seeking a consistent global dataset must choose among conflicting products, potentially propagating uncertainty into area estimates and temporal trend analyses.

Ensemble modeling offers an alternative to address this challenge. Instead of treating discrepancies among land cover products as noise, ensemble methods leverage the complementary strengths of individual datasets (Mienye and Sun 2022). Each product may perform optimally in specific regions or land cover types, depending on the suitability of its training data, input imagery, and classification algorithms. Machine learning enables the identification and modeling of spatially varying reliability patterns from reference data, effectively weighting each input based on its performance across different contexts.

This study presents a framework for ensemble-based global annual land cover mapping at 30 m resolution from 2000 to 2025+. A random forest classifier integrates multiple land cover products and environmental covariates, learning where each input performs best. The framework implements rigorous quality control for training data, combining Bayesian inference and confident learning to mitigate label noise. In addition to a discrete land cover classification, it generates class probability surfaces and pixel-level uncertainty estimates that support transparent area estimation, change detection, and downstream uncertainty propagation. This addresses a critical gap in current land cover mapping: the need for methods that systematically leverage the collective information content of diverse classification products while providing spatially explicit confidence measures for area estimation, change detection, and statistical reporting.

2. Method

The framework proceeds through seven stages. First, *data compilation* assembles two input streams: (a) the reference samples from Simoes et al. (2025), initially comprising about 77 million training points spanning 2000–2022 with global coverage compiled from GLanCE (Stanimirova et al. 2023), Dynamic World (Brown et al. 2022) and WorldCereal (Van Tricht et al. 2023); and (b) predictor covariates including existing land cover global and national products, as well as environmental variables such as median vegetation height from Global Pasture Watch (GPW; Parente et al. 2024), terrain derivatives from the Global Ensemble Digital Terrain Model (GEDTM30; Ho et al. 2025), and climate data, including monthly land surface temperature. This multi-source predictor stack enables the model to leverage both categorical classifications and continuous probability surfaces. Second, *legend harmonization* crosswalks training point labels to a unified 14-class target system, balancing thematic detail with classification feasibility while maintaining compatibility with IPCC reporting categories. Third, *space-time overlay* extracts covariate values for each reference point at its location and year, linking training samples to the corresponding land cover product labels and environmental conditions for that observation.

Fourth, *quality control* addresses label noise inherent in the multi-source reference compilations

through two complementary approaches. Bayesian map fusion reconciles disagreements among source datasets by leveraging user’s and producer’s accuracies from each source to construct class-conditional priors, then applies Bayes’ theorem to compute posterior probabilities for the true class of each point based on evidence from multiple maps. CleanLab’s confident learning framework (Northcutt, Jiang, and Chuang 2021) provides a data-driven validation by comparing labels against out-of-sample predictions from cross-validated random forest models, generating label quality scores that quantify agreement between assigned labels and feature-space evidence. Points with low posterior probability and low CleanLab quality scores are removed, along with spatial duplicates identified through proximity analysis.

Fifth, *random forest ensemble modeling* trains a classifier using the cleaned and filtered reference data, with land cover products, and the additional environmental covariates as features. The model captures spatially varying patterns from the different inputs, learning where each source provides reliable information. By combining multiple complementary datasets within a single predictive framework, the ensemble approach maximizes the collective information content of all inputs while enabling robust, spatially explicit predictions of global land cover. Sixth, *model validation* evaluates the performance of the random forest ensemble using variable importance analysis and cross-validation metrics. Accuracy is assessed following standard protocols, including overall accuracy, class-specific user’s and producer’s accuracy, and F1-scores. Pixel-level uncertainty is quantified by the variance in class probabilities across ensemble trees, yielding spatially explicit confidence estimates that reflect the reliability of individual predictions. Seventh, *data production* applies the trained model to generate annual land cover predictions across the entire 2000–2025+ time-series at 30 m resolution. The outputs include a discrete classification, class probability surfaces for all land cover classes, and derived uncertainty layers.

3. Preliminary results

The results presented here correspond to early iterations of the method and may vary as analyses are refined. Pilot implementations over the conterminous United States (CONUS) demonstrate the framework. The US pilot achieves 74% and 86% overall accuracy on both level 1 and level 2 land cover classifications using independent validation data. Table 1 presents class-specific accuracy metrics for the level 2 classification.

The first results for variable importance show high feature importance for GPW covariates, particularly median short vegetation height in natural/semi-natural grassland and cultivated grassland. GLAD global maps of cropland extent and specific classes from the GLC_FCS30D land cover products follow these. Figure 1 shows an example of the predicted land cover classes for the pilot area for the year 2020, while Figure 2 illustrates the entropy map for the same year, reflecting spatial patterns of classification confidence across the pilot area. The framework produces classified maps, class-probability layers for all 14 classes, and spatially explicit uncertainty estimates, enabling users to assess reliability at every pixel and propagate uncertainty into downstream analyses.

Temporal consistency across the full 2000–2025+ time-series, including evaluation of year-to-year transition smoothness and detection of spurious changes, is planned as a key validation step once

Table 1: Class-specific accuracy metrics for the US pilot. UA = User’s accuracy (precision), PA = Producer’s accuracy (recall), F1 = F1-score.

	Class	UA	PA	F1
	1. Developed/Urban	0.775	0.674	0.721
	2. Cropland	0.852	0.885	0.868
	3. Grassland and shrubland			
	3.1 Natural Semi-Natural Grassland	0.856	0.556	0.674
	3.2 Cultivated Grassland/Pasture	0.641	0.576	0.607
	3.3 Shrubland	0.536	0.643	0.584
	4. Forest			
	4.1 Deciduous Forest	0.622	0.754	0.682
	4.2 Evergreen Forest	0.641	0.728	0.682
	4.3 Mixed Forest	0.632	0.472	0.540
	5. Barren			
	5.1 Bare Soil	0.798	0.777	0.787
	5.2 Rock Outcrops	0.959	0.875	0.915
	5.3 Shifting Sand	0.848	0.894	0.870
	5.4 Permanent Snow/Ice	0.829	0.829	0.829
	6. Wetland	0.968	0.713	0.821
	7. Water	0.834	0.976	0.900

global annual production is complete. The inference pipeline is parallelized across 16 compute servers; preliminary benchmarks for the CONUS pilot indicate a processing time of approximately 1.5 hours per year of output, making complete time-series production operationally feasible.

4. Conclusion

We presented preliminary results from a spatiotemporal ensemble framework for annual 30 m global land cover mapping that integrates multiple existing products and environmental covariates via random forest classification. Quality control combining Bayesian map fusion and confident learning reduces label noise across a large multi-source training dataset, and outputs include discrete classifications, per-class probability surfaces, and pixel-level uncertainty estimates. A pilot over CONUS achieves 74% and 86% overall accuracy at level 1 and level 2, with strong results for cropland (F1-score = 0.868), water (F1-score = 0.900), and rock outcrops (F1-score = 0.915). Extension to global coverage, evaluation of temporal consistency across the 2000–2025+ time-series, and further refinement of training data quality are the immediate next steps. All outputs will be released as open data to support reproducible land monitoring and environmental reporting.

5. Funding

The Open-Earth-Monitor Cyberinfrastructure project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101059548.

Figure 1: Predicted land cover map for the CONUS pilot area, year 2020. The map displays the 14-class classification produced by the ensemble framework.

Figure 2: Entropy for the CONUS pilot area, year 2020. Higher entropy values indicate greater uncertainty in the ensemble classification.

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